

MAGNETICALLY ACTUATED FUNCTIONAL GRADIENT NANOCOMPOSITES FOR STRONG AND DURABLE BIOINSPIRED INTERFACES/SURFACES

Zhengzhi Wang^{1*}, Xiaoming Shi², Houbing Huang², Chenmin Yao³, Wen Xie¹, Cui Huang³, Ping Gu⁴,
Xingqiao Ma², Zuoqi Zhang¹, and Long-qing Chen⁵

¹ Department of Engineering Mechanics, School of Civil Engineering, Wuhan University, Wuhan, Hubei 430072, China (zhengzhi.wang@whu.edu.cn)

² Department of Physics, University of Science and Technology Beijing, Beijing 100083, China

³ School of Stomatology, Wuhan University, Wuhan, Hubei 430072, China

⁴ Department of Modern Mechanics, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, Anhui 230072, China

⁵ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, The Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA 16802, USA

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ABSTRACT

Biological systems have evolved various functional gradients within interfacial and surface regions to fulfil unusual mechanically-challenging demands [1-3]. Exploring these design principles of nature materials into practice remains difficult, however, due to the lack of proper processing technique for analogous gradients within narrow regions. Here we report a facile and cost-effective technique enabling the construction of a variety of bioinspired gradient interfaces/surfaces that are not accessible using state-of-the-art technologies. This technique utilizes magnetic actuation to control spatial distribution of nano-sized reinforcements inside polymer matrices, being able to generate functional gradient nanocomposites (FGNCs) with controllable stiff-to-soft or soft-to-stiff transition within regions as narrow as 10 microns (Fig. 1). We demonstrate the robustness and universality of this technique by implementing the FGNCs into three mechanically-challenging applications: 1) functional gradient interlayer for strong, intact, and ultra-durable jointing between dissimilar materials; 2) functional gradient coating for hard, wear-resistant, and long-lasting surface protections; and 3) functional gradient pillars for flexible, structurally stable, and reusable biomimetic adhesives. The presented study opens a new route for designing and developing materials/structures with optimized performances by simply modifying the spatial distributions of material composition. This route can potentially be integrated into advanced manufacturing techniques [4, 5] and applied to numerous surface/interface fields to achieve unparalleled combinations among various critical properties.

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Figure 1: Magnetically-actuated functional gradient nanocomposites (FGNCs): theoretical predictions and comparison with experiments. (a) Calculated magnetic field (H_{az}) and force (F_{mz}) for a single nanoparticle (NP) along z direction as a function of NP-magnet distance. (b) Computational (Com.) and experimental (Exp.) results of 1D NPs concentration profiles within 10 μm region under selected low (50 mT), medium (150 mT), and high (300 mT) magnetic fields for three contrasting gradient architectures (initial particle concentration: 18 vol.%). Corresponding 2D distributions of the NPs are displayed in (c), (d), and (e) for respectively 50, 150, and 300 mT magnetic field with left column obtained by Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) observations in experiments and right column obtained by computer simulations.